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Uncovering major types of deforestation frontiers across the world's tropical dry woodlands

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ABSTRACT

Tropical dry woodlands are rapidly being lost to agricultural expansion, but how deforestation dynamics play out in these woodlands remains poorly understood. Here, we develop an approach to detect and map high-level patterns of deforestation frontiers, i.e., the expansion of woodland loss, across continents in unprecedented spatio-temporal detail. Deforestation in tropical dry woodlands is pervasive, with over 71 Mha lost since 2000 and one third of wooded areas located in deforestation frontiers. Over 24.3 Mha of deforestation frontiers fall into what we term 'rampant frontiers'. These are characterized by drastic woodland loss and conditions favorable for capital-intensive agriculture, as seen in the South American Chaco and Southeast Asia. We find many active and emerging frontiers (~59% of all frontiers), mostly in the understudied dry woodlands of Africa and Asia, where greater frontier monitoring is needed. Our approach enables consistent, repeatable frontier monitoring, and our global frontier typology fosters comparative research and context-specific policy making.

INTRODUCTION

Tropical deforestation is the principal driver of biodiversity loss as well as contributing to climate change, the spread of zoonotic diseases, and the widespread degradation of ecosystem services which disproportionately affects marginalized communities^{1,2}. A major cause of deforestation is agricultural expansion^{3,4}, by different types of smallholders and agribusinesses^{3,4}. These diverse

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forms of agricultural expansion, embedded in different social-ecological contexts, produce deforestation frontiers with heterogeneous severity, speed, and spatial patterns of forest loss⁵⁻⁷. Navigating and structuring this complexity remains a major challenge for sustainability science⁸. Particularly, identifying high-level, recurring frontier types is essential for the more context-specific policy responses often called for to govern frontier regions⁹. Likewise, identifying high-level frontier types would enable learning and comparative research across geographies¹⁰, and help to build theory in sustainability science⁸. However, whether such generalizable, high-level deforestation frontier types exist remains highly unclear.

Three factors have contributed to this knowledge gap. First, there are major geographical research biases towards a few specific regions¹¹, while many others remain entirely overlooked¹². Second, research on deforestation frontiers has typically focussed on investigating dynamics within certain places or regions, such as in Amazonia¹³, Indonesia¹⁴, or the Congo Basin¹⁵, but there is a clear lack of cross-regional and comparative assessments¹⁶. Third, global satellite-based time-series products describing forest and woodland loss at high spatial resolution have only recently become available¹⁷. These data could provide deep insights into *how* deforestation frontiers advance and help to identify typical, recurrent patterns of deforestation frontiers. Recently, detecting and assessing such archetypical human-environment interactions has become a major focus in sustainability science^{18,19}, including for identifying static land systems²⁰ or driver/outcome constellations^{8,21,22}. Here, we pioneer the use of archetype analyses to identify the major, recurring patterns in global deforestation frontiers.

Deforestation frontiers, in particular, are weakly understood in the world's tropical woodlands, (defined in our manuscript as including tropical dry forests, shrublands, and wooded savannas with more than 10% tree cover). When compared with humid forests, these woodlands are overlooked by researchers, policy-makers and the general public²³⁻²⁵. Yet these ecosystems harbor unique biodiversity, including many endemic species, and are some of the last refuges for iconic megafauna²⁴⁻²⁶. Tropical dry woodlands provide important ecosystem services that sustain the livelihoods of hundreds of millions of people and store globally relevant amounts of carbon^{24,26,27}. Despite this, many woodland regions today are global deforestation hotspots¹⁷, including in South America (e.g., Gran Chaco²⁸, Cerrado²⁹) and Southeast Asia (e.g., Cambodia^{30,31}). There is also increasing evidence that the same pervasive dynamics are emerging in African dry woodlands, such as in the Miombo woodlands^{17,25,32}. This translates into an urgent need to identify and monitor how deforestation frontiers expand into woodlands to allow for timely policy responses.

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We developed a methodology to identify and map deforestation frontiers, and applied it to carry out a global, high-resolution assessment of frontier dynamics in tropical dry woodlands.

Specifically, we used a 20-year time series of tree loss to develop a consistent, high-resolution set of frontier metrics describing frontier severity, patterns, and development stage. Based on this, we established a nested typology of deforestation frontiers, allowing us to (1) map archetypical frontiers across all tropical dry woodlands, (2) describe the socio-ecological characteristics of major frontier types, and (3) assess the research effort across these types.

RESULTS

Major frontier types. Our analytical framework to typify and map deforestation frontiers in tropical dry woodlands involved four main steps (Figure 1). In step 1, we detected candidate areas for frontiers for the period 2000 to 2020. In step 2, we derived a set of metrics characterizing the deforestation process itself, which we then used in step 3 to develop three thematic typologies describing the severity, spatio-temporal patterns, and development stage of frontiers. Finally, in step 4, we grouped these thematic types into frontier archetypes.

Figure 1- Analytical framework to derive major deforestation frontiers in the world's tropical dry

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woodlands in four main steps. Step 1 detects frontier processes, step 2 derives metrics to describe frontiers, step 3 builds frontier typologies, and step 4 develops frontier archetypes.

Applying this framework across the world's tropical dry woodlands, according to our definition (Supplementary Figure 1), revealed that woodland grid cells occupied 1,884.97 million hectares (Mha) and contained about 1,044.13 Mha of woodland in the year 2000. We identified 577.36 Mha of woodland cells undergoing substantial deforestation processes from 2001 to 2020 (~31% of woodland cells in 2000), accounting for around 71.7 Mha of woodlands loss (92% of total loss). Of the frontier area, three-quarters (76.5%) is in the tropical and subtropical grasslands, savannas and shrublands biome, highlighting the importance for considering this biome when assessing woodland loss, with the remaining quarter (23.5%) in the tropical and subtropical dry broad-leaved forests biome. Deforestation frontiers occurred across the globe, with the highest prevalence in South America (46.2% of total frontier area in tropical dry woodlands) followed by Africa (43.8%), Asia (5.0%), North America (3.9%) and Australia and Oceania (here: Australia, 1.1%).

Three typologies of deforestation frontiers. In step 3, we combined the frontier metrics from step 2 that described how deforestation progressed in space and time. This resulted in our thematic frontier typologies (see Methods, Supplementary Text 1, and Supplementary Figure 2 and 3). We combined metrics pairwise to yield three typologies describing the severity, spatio-temporal patterns, and development stage of frontiers. We classified each metric into three classes, resulting in nine frontier types for each of our three themed typologies. Our first typology was geared towards assessing deforestation severity, combining metrics of baseline woodland and the percentage of total woodland loss (Figure 2, Supplementary Figure 4). Frontiers with high woodland cover and low woodland loss were most extensive (260.00 Mha, 45.0% of total frontier area), followed by medium woodland cover and low woodland loss (125.75 Mha, 21.8%). These frontiers were most common in central and southern Africa (e.g., Northern Congolian Forest-Savanna, Central Zambezian wet Miombo woodlands) and North America (e.g., Puerto Rican dry forests). Over 40.02 Mha were classified as having high severity, having both a high percentage of total woodland loss and high and medium baseline woodland (4.6% and 2.4%, respectively). High severity frontiers occurred mostly in South America (e.g., Dry Chaco), and were more prevalent within South America and Asia (e.g., Southeast Indochina dry forests and Southern Vietnam lowland dry forests in Asia).

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Figure 2 – Typology according to the severity of deforestation frontiers in tropical dry woodlands, based on baseline and percentage of total woodland loss (A). Inset show zoom in to the Gran Chaco (B), Cerrado & Caatinga (C), Miombo and Mopane woodlands (D), West African dry forest (E) and Indochina tropical dry forests (F).

Our second typology explored spatio-temporal patterns of woodland loss, combining metrics of speed of woodland loss and fragmentation (Figure 3, Supplementary Figure 4). The most common type of frontier had medium speed of woodland loss with high levels of fragmentation (141.20 Mha, 24.5% of total frontier area). This type was more prevalent within African (e.g., Guinean forest-savanna and Western Congolian Dry Forests) and parts of South American (e.g., Ecuadorian dry forests and Lara-Falcón dry forests) frontiers. 85.00 Mha were classified as slow frontiers with high fragmentation (14.7%), and were more prevalent within North America (e.g., Chiapas Depression and Central American Dry Forests) and parts of South America (e.g., Cauca Valley and Patía Valley Dry Forests). 51.54 Mha were classified as fast frontiers with medium fragmentation (8.9%), mainly within Australia (e.g., Cape York peninsula), South America (e.g., Dry Chaco) and Asia frontiers (e.g., Southeast Indochina Dry Forests).

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Figure 3 – Typology according to the spatio-temporal pattern deforestation frontiers in tropical dry woodlands, based on speed and fragmentation of woodland loss (A). Inset show zoom in to the Gran Chaco (B), Cerrado & Caatinga (C), Miombo and Mopane woodlands (D), West African dry forest (E) and Indochina tropical dry forests (F).

Our third typology explored the development stage of frontiers, combining metrics of activeness and remaining woodland (Figure 4, Supplementary Figure 4). The most prevalent types here were old frontiers with little woodland left (101.43 Mha, 17.6%) and active frontiers with high levels of woodland left (105.24 Mha, 18.2% of total frontier area). Old frontiers with little woodland left were more prevalent within Australia (e.g., Kimberly tropical savanna), South America (e.g., Caatinga) and North American (e.g., Sierra de la Laguna dry forests). Active frontiers with high levels of remaining woodland were more prevalent within African frontiers (e.g., Western and Southern Congolian forest-savanna, and Angolan miombo woodlands). 105.02 Mha were classified as emerging frontiers (18.42%), mostly in Africa (e.g., Guinean forest-savanna and Northern Congolian forest-savanna). In total, 339.89 Mha were classified as active or emerging frontiers (58.9%), most commonly in Africa and Asia.

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Figure 4 – Typology according to the development stage of deforestation frontiers in tropical dry woodlands, based on activeness and woodland left (A). Inset show zoom in to the Gran Chaco (B), Cerrado & Caatinga (C), Miombo and Mopane woodlands (D), West African dry forest (E) and Indochina tropical dry forests (F).

Archetypal deforestation frontiers. Our final step combined the frontier types identified by our three themed typologies (severity, spatio-temporal patterns, development stage) to identify frontier archetypes, defined here as high-level frontier patterns across geographical contexts (step 4, Figure 1). By qualitatively grouping combinations of types from our typologies, we derived five such frontier archetypes: inactive frontiers, consolidated frontiers, fragmented frontiers, looming frontiers and rampant frontiers (Figure 5, Supplementary Figure 5). Importantly, the goal here was not to characterize and classify all frontier cells but to group those frontier cells that clearly undergo recurrent and comparable patterns. In other words, our typologies (characterizing frontier processes in all cells) and archetype analyses (identifying high-level and recurring frontier patterns) should be seen as complementary.

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Figure 5 – Archetypes of deforestation frontiers in tropical dry woodlands (A). Inset show zoom in to the Gran Chaco (B), Cerrado & Caatinga (C), Miombo and Mopane woodlands (D), West African dry forest (E) and Indochina tropical dry forests (F).

Inactive frontiers correspond to old frontiers with high baseline woodland, yet still have high remaining areas of woodland. This archetype covered about 75.33 Mha (13.0% of all areas identified as frontiers), mostly in Africa (e.g., northern Congolian Forest-Savanna and Zambezian-Limpopo woodlands).

Consolidated frontiers have little remaining woodland, are old and deforestation is relatively slow (Figure 5, Supplementary Figure 4). This archetype corresponded to 68.56 Mha (11.9% of all areas identified as frontiers) and was most prevalent within North America (e.g., Sierra de la Laguna Dry Forests), South America (e.g., Tumbes-Piura Dry Forests), and Australia (e.g., Kimberly tropical savanna).

Fragmented frontiers are active frontiers producing highly fragmented woodland loss patterns, mainly in Africa (e.g., Southern and Western Congolian forest-savanna) and South

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America (e.g., Maranhão Babaçu forests, Lara-Falcón dry forests). This archetype covered about 114.43 Mha (19.8% of all areas identified as frontiers).

Looming frontiers are slowly to medium speed emerging frontiers (Figure 5, Supplementary Figure 4). This archetype covered about 91.82 Mha (15.9% of all areas identified as frontiers) and was most prevalent within Africa (e.g., Guinean and Victoria Basin Forest-savanna) and Australia (e.g., New Caledonia Dry Forests).

Finally, *rampant frontiers*, refer to rapidly advancing frontiers in situations with high baseline woodland and high woodland loss. This archetype expanded over about 24.3 Mha (4.2% of all areas identified as frontiers) and such frontiers were most prevalent within South America (e.g., Dry Chaco, Chiquitano dry forests), followed by Asia (e.g., Southeast Indochina and Southern Vietnam lowland Dry Forests). The remaining areas classified as frontiers in tropical dry woodlands regions, but not falling into one of our five archetypes, corresponded to about 202.92 Mha (35.1% of all areas identified as frontiers).

Social-ecological characteristics of frontiers. To characterize the social-ecological context of our identified frontiers, we described them according to a set of spatial determinants, selected based on prevalent frontier theories (see Methods). Specifically, we determined the key characteristics of our frontiers based on proximate drivers of woodland loss, capital inputs to farming (captured by field size), market integration (captured by accessibility), and agro-ecological suitability (Figures 2-4, Supplementary Figure 6). Inactive frontiers mostly showed patterns of smallholder agriculture, very small field size, very low accessibility, and marginal suitability (Figure 6). Consolidated frontiers mostly showed patterns of smallholder agriculture, large field size, high accessibility, and marginal suitability. Fragmented frontiers mostly showed patterns of smallholder agriculture, very small field size, very high accessibility, and marginal suitability. Looming frontiers mostly showed patterns of smallholder agriculture, diverse field size, varied accessibility, and marginal suitability. Rampant frontiers mostly showed patterns of commodity driven woodland loss, large field size, very low accessibility, and moderate to marginal suitability. Other frontiers, that did not fall into the five archetypes shown in Figure 6, showed patterns of smallholder agriculture, large field size, very high accessibility, and marginal suitability.

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Figure 6 – Characteristics of frontier archetypes according to the social-ecological variables describing frontier dynamics (see Supplementary Text 2). Bubble size refers to the share of total archetype area falling in that combination of archetype and variable class, whereas bubble color refers to the area in Mha covered by that combination.

Research effort across frontier archetypes. To assess research effort across our frontier archetypes in tropical dry woodlands, we carried out a systematic literature search and identified 155 relevant studies (see Methods). Of these, 35 and 49 studies only analyzed deforestation before and after 2000, respectively. Moreover, 126 focused on national to subnational scales, while 29 studied woodlands deforestation across several countries or continents. The greatest number of studies was recoded in South America (66 records), followed by Africa (52), North America (19), Asia (7), and Australia (1). The most researched ecoregions were Cerrado (36), Dry Chaco (35), and the West Sudanian Savanna (23), while the least-researched ecoregions were found in Australia and Asia, notably Southeast Indochina Dry Forests (4) and Central Indochina Dry Forests (5) (see Supplementary Figure 8). Assessing the relative research effort across our types and archetypes showed that rampant frontiers received the most research attention while the least researched archetypes were inactive frontiers (Supplementary Table 3). Research in South America showed a positive bias towards rampant frontiers, while in the other continents this bias was negative (Supplementary Table 3).

DISCUSSION

Tropical dry woodlands are under high and rising pressure globally, yet have been neglected by sustainability research, policy-making, and planning¹². Here, we developed a

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generalizable approach to detect, map, and describe deforestation frontiers in high spatial and temporal detail. Applying this approach to all tropical dry woodlands globally yielded four major insights. First, the loss of woodlands is widespread, with more than 71 Mha of tropical dry woodlands gone since 2000 and one-third of all woodland areas within deforestation frontiers. However, existing research efforts have focused mostly on deforestation in the humid tropics with only a few studies in tropical dry woodlands, highlighting the urgent need to ramp up research there. Second, rampant frontiers are widespread and chiefly associated with expanding commodity agriculture, which, given the rising demand for agricultural commodities, suggests that pressure on these woodlands will continue to stay high. Third, much of the world's tropical dry woodlands fall into early frontier stages, with many emerging frontiers in Africa, most of which remain overlooked and understudied. Together, this emphasizes the need for monitoring and forward-looking sustainability planning in those regions as frontier dynamics unfold. Finally, despite the high diversity in deforestation speed, patterns, and drivers in frontiers, we identified five common, high-level archetypes of frontier dynamics that occur globally. These archetypes provide a basis for comparative research and cross-regional learning in sustainability science. More generally, our frontier metrics and typologies provide a flexible, repeatable, and scalable approach to foster more context specificity in research, policy-making, and land-use planning in frontier regions.

Deforestation frontiers occurred in a third of our study area, leading to the loss of over 71 Mha of tropical dry woodlands over the period 2000 - 2020. Over the same period, tropical moist forests lost about 147 Mha^{17,33}. Yet, despite major woodland losses and the huge social-ecological impacts these losses entail^{1,24,27}, research efforts have been lagging behind those in other threatened regions, such as tropical moist forests^{12,24}. Moreover, among understudied active frontiers in tropical dry woodlands, those in Africa and Asia are particularly under-researched in contrast with old frontiers in South America. This geographic bias can be explained by structural inequalities in research institutions, access, and agendas across continents¹¹, the preferences of funding organizations, and because general deforestation studies often do not separate dry and moist ecosystems³⁴. Fostering tropical dry woodland research, particularly on Asian and African frontiers, would allow for timely policy and management responses in these threatened ecosystems.

Our second main finding was that rampant frontiers were mostly associated with conditions typical for capitalized commodity agriculture (commodity-driven woodland loss representing most of the deforestation, large field sizes, higher agro-ecological suitability, low

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accessibility areas). Commodity production drives rampant frontiers in several of those regions, such as the Dry Chaco²⁸ where export-oriented soybean production and cattle ranching have created one of the world's most severe deforestation hotspots^{35,36}. Commodity production is likely a key frontier driver in less-well researched regions such as the Chiquitano forests, Venezuelan Llanos, or Indochina Dry Forests as well^{16,30,37}. It is well recognized that commodity production, particularly for international markets, is increasingly driving tropical deforestation^{36,38}. Actors operating in commodity frontiers typically have the capital to overcome accessibility constraints, operate over large areas to leverage internal economies of scale, are active across international borders, and target remote regions where land prices are still low^{36,39}. Policy responses, such as land-use planning, often lag behind in rampant frontier regions³⁰, and when frontiers slow down due to local resistance, regulation, or spatial constraints^{40,41}, land-use pressure might be displaced to other regions^{29,30}. Rapid regulatory action should therefore be deployed in rampant frontiers, combining area-based interventions (e.g., zoning and native habitat protection) as well as actor-focussed ones (e.g., supply chain agreements)^{16,30}.

Many African frontiers were classified as fragmented or inactive frontiers, associated with conditions typical for smallholder regions (high prevalence of smallholder agriculture and small field sizes)^{4,6}. Smallholders use land for subsistence, employment, and income through the exploitation of forest resources or the expansion of small-scale agriculture that feeds both local and global markets^{32,42}. Fragmented frontiers thus likely represent active frontiers driven by smallholders, and occur mostly in more accessible areas. In contrast, inactive frontiers are no longer active and might reflect pioneer efforts to advance into poorly accessible areas^{36,43}. Such inactive frontiers could also indicate areas where initial waves of resource exploration have built a technical, social or institutional basis for future, rapid reactivation⁴⁴. The final archetype identified was consolidated frontiers, where frontier dynamics slow down due to the scarcity of remaining forest. This archetype was common in South America, where some regions (e.g. Caatinga) have a long history of deforestation⁴⁵.

A key advantage of our methodology is that it can uncover emerging frontiers, of which we found many, particularly in African woodlands. These frontiers emerge because of the availability of unexploited land suitable for agriculture, growing population densities, high dependency on woodland resources for energy, and possible investments from actors leaving consolidated frontier regions^{1,4}. Frontiers in Africa currently develop under varying trends, with large-scale operations increasing in some areas such as the Miombo forests^{16,32}. Within emerging frontiers, we identified an archetype of looming frontiers that develop slowly yet are

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ubiquitous across Africa. Improved monitoring of woodland loss in these looming frontiers would provide early warning signs of frontiers that have the potential to become rampant. Given what is at stake, including some of the last wild places with intact communities of unique megafauna²⁴, as well as vast areas where local communities depend on forests and woodlands for their livelihoods¹, forward-looking sustainability planning of African emerging frontiers is of the utmost importance.

Typologies and archetype approaches are a powerful tool to identify and map high-level human-nature interactions. The archetypes approach that we developed can be useful for at least three purposes. First, our approach allows us to develop policy responses appropriate for specific, yet recurring contexts. For example, while in emerging frontiers there is an urgent need to focus on increasing protection and ensuring the rights of Indigenous peoples and local communities, in consolidated frontiers it may be more important to plan restoration^{8,16}. Similarly, while supply-chain measures are likely key in rampant frontiers driven by agribusiness actors, in fragmented frontiers dominated by smallholders, policies fostering local participation by recognising local needs, knowledge, and constraints could help protect remaining forests^{46,47}. Second, archetypes can enable learning and comparative research across geographies^{10,18}. For example, we can apply lessons from successful and failed interventions in South American frontiers to socially and ecologically similar conditions in Africa, or more generally to prevent leakage outcomes of policies against rampant frontiers^{29,30}. Third, archetypes can be useful to build theory in sustainability science⁸, as our types and archetypes are boundary objects that can intersect with additional information, can be used to compile and synthesize cases studies across frontier types, or can be used to foster understanding of causal effects and mechanisms underlying deforestation frontiers^{10,18}. This could reveal, for instance, when and why frontiers emerge, under which conditions they become rampant, or when inactive frontiers are reactivated.

We developed a typology of deforestation frontiers for tropical dry woodlands, using the best available data. Our approach is open and flexible, and while we derived our typologies for the purpose of our paper, our methodology can easily be adjusted or refined to generate other typologies and archetypes for different applications. Likewise, our approach can easily absorb updated datasets to consistently trace frontier dynamics and archetypes over time. Our work adds to recent advances in global studies of deforestation frontiers¹⁶, by considering frontier dynamics, and by extending beyond only mapping deforestation hotspots (~92% of forest loss in tropical dry woodlands fall under our definition of frontiers). Nevertheless, a few limitations need

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to be mentioned. First, recent work has shown that tree cover in dryland areas can be underrepresented^{48,49}. The Global Forest Change (GFC) dataset we use here is no exception and potentially underestimates tree cover at low tree densities⁵⁰. The result would be a subsequent underestimation of frontier dynamics in very sparsely wooded ecosystems. Second, the GFC dataset does not distinguish between native woodland and tree plantations. Retaining these areas is important, as frontier processes in some tropical dry woodlands include the expansion of tree plantations^{31,51}. As a result, we cannot rule out the overestimation of frontier activeness in the few regions where tree plantations are widespread (e.g., Uruguayan Savanna, Vietnam Lowland Dry Forests, southern Cerrado⁵²). Third, some forest loss might be due to fires, which are often an indication of the frontier-making process^{8,37} but might also occur naturally. Fourth, as with any global analyses, uncertainty remains, and our results are therefore likely most insightful when interpreting the broad-scale dynamics we uncover across the world's tropical dry woodlands. We explicitly caution against interpreting and analyzing our results at the level of individual cells or localities. Lastly, to generate our archetypes we qualitatively grouped frontier types, combining both deductive and inductive reasoning. This allowed us to highlight common patterns across geographies while building on prior knowledge and theories. Our analysis is open for expansion and updating as tree loss time series grows. Currently, about ~35% of frontier cells were not grouped into any frontier archetype, illustrating the diversity of frontier processes in tropical dry woodlands. This diversity is better represented in our three detailed thematic typologies.

Deforestation frontiers are rapidly advancing in tropical dry woodlands, driving biodiversity loss, degrading global ecosystem services, and impacting local livelihoods. To better understand these dynamics, we developed an analytical and operational framework to identify recurrent frontier patterns, which we applied here to provide the first typology and map of global frontier dynamics in tropical dry woodlands. This confirmed that those woodlands are being lost rapidly, that these losses are weakly understood and poorly studied, and that particularly rampant woodland losses are associated with commodity agriculture, particularly in South America and Asia. However, our approach also uncovered the importance of emerging African frontiers, many of which remain virtually unstudied, highlighting the urgent need for more targeted research and sustainability planning. More generally, the frontier types and archetypes we identified can facilitate comparative studies of frontier development, contextualized policy making and planning, and cross-regional learning. Our approach is generalizable and repeatable across scales, time, and geographies, and its value will increase over time as forest loss time series grow, providing an innovative tool for monitoring deforestation frontier

dynamics. Together, this constitutes a major step towards governing deforestation frontiers and promoting more sustainable land use in the world's tropical dry forests.

METHODS

Tropical Dry Woodlands definition. Many definitions of tropical dry forests or woodlands have been proposed^{23,24}. Here, we followed previous work on these systems globally^{23,53,54} and used an inclusive definition. Specifically, we focused on all forests, shrublands, and savannas falling into two biomes according to the updated biome classification of Dinerstein, et al.⁵⁵: (1) tropical and subtropical dry broad-leaved forests, and (2) tropical and subtropical grasslands, savannas and shrublands. Within these biomes, we defined woodlands as all areas with a minimum tree cover threshold of 10% in the year 2000, based on the GFC dataset. Tree cover in this dataset refers to vegetation taller than 5 m^{17,53}. Thus, all forests, shrublands and savannas exceeding this threshold are collectively referred to as tropical dry woodlands for the purpose of our manuscript.

Tropical dry woodlands are generally characterized by a marked dry season of three months or more, with average annual rainfall from 250 to 2000 mm, as well as often mesotrophic soils^{23,53,56}. This results in typical, diverse vegetation structure within these woodlands, with semi-deciduous and deciduous trees, drought resistant shrubs or succulents, as well as grasses. There are strong social-ecological differences both within and among woodland regions^{23,53,56}. Tropical dry woodlands have long been a preferred zone for human settlement, due to favorable agro-climatic conditions, resulting in various degrees of transformation. Tropical dry woodlands regions therefore differ in terms of land-use history, dominant land-use practices, or different use of fire as a management tool⁵⁷. Importantly, some tropical dry woodland regions have retained megafauna, such as elephants or giraffes, which can substantially impact on vegetation patterns, while megafauna has been lost from other regions historically or recently⁵⁸.

A major activity in tropical dry woodlands is agriculture, including cropping and rearing livestock. Agriculture has caused major transformations of these regions, both historically and recently²³. Historically, these transformations were mainly driven by expanding subsistence agriculture, including slash-and-burn agriculture²⁴. While subsistence agriculture still dominates over large swaths of tropical dry woodlands^{27,59}, land-use change in many of these regions today is driven by market-oriented actors expanding industrialized agriculture to produce

commodities for domestic and international markets^{28,60}. This has caused major tropical dry woodland loss in many regions, including the South American Chaco and Cerrado (e.g., soy, maize, beef), Indochina Dry Forests (e.g., rubber, coffee) or Zambia (e.g., tobacco and cotton) which have recently experienced some of the highest deforestation rates worldwide^{16,17}. Tropical dry woodlands are additionally exploited for their forest resources, including firewood extraction, timber extraction, and charcoal production^{56,61}. Fuelwood remains an important energy source in many countries of Africa, translating into a major driver of woodland loss there^{56,61}.

Developing a typology of deforestation frontiers. To typify deforestation frontiers in tropical dry woodlands, we developed a four-step analytical framework (Figure 1).

In step 1, to map deforestation frontiers in tropical dry woodlands, we relied on baseline tree cover and annual tree loss time-series from 2000 to 2020 from Global Forest Change (GFC)¹⁷. We aggregated the data from 30x30 m² resolution to a resolution of 3x3 km². The GFC dataset has an overall accuracy of >99%¹⁷ and aggregating these data to a lower resolution increases accuracy further^{62,63}. The aggregation resulted in an annual time series of woodland loss for the period 2000 to 2020, at an unprecedented spatial and temporal resolution of analysis of deforestation frontiers. Our subsequent analyses were based on this annual tree loss time series. Our tree loss analysis included both woodland conversion and degradation processes, which we jointly refer to as deforestation. We did not include tree gain data from GFC, because (1) these are not available annually, (2) are not available for our full analysis period, (3) are less accurate than tree loss, and (4) lump together gains in tree plantations, tree crops, and natural woodland regrowth⁶⁴. Although assessing tree cover gain in frontiers would be interesting, there is currently no robust dataset allowing us to do this at the spatial and temporal resolution of our analysis. To identify areas potentially qualifying as frontiers, we first selected all cells that had more than 5% of forest cover in 2000, to exclude areas with very low initial forest cover and with little potential to display frontier processes. Next, we selected cells that had an average annual percentage of forest loss of at least 0.5% within a consecutive five-year period¹³. This ensures potential frontier areas are in line with common conceptualisation of frontier as progressively expanding⁴³ and through this causing considerable forest loss.

In step 2, to characterise deforestation frontiers, we created a set of frontier metrics, based on our aggregated time series of woodland loss and cover. These frontier metrics go substantially beyond conventional change analyses as they represent multiple facets of frontier expansion, allowing for a deeper characterization of frontiers in space and time. Specifically, we derived metrics capturing (1) the severity of the frontier (i.e., percentage of total woodland loss,

baseline woodland), (2) the spatio-temporal pattern of frontier development (i.e., speed of frontier, fragmentation of woodland loss), and (3) the development stage of frontiers (i.e., frontier activeness, woodland left). We calculated percentage of total woodland loss by dividing total woodland loss by baseline woodland, where the latter is woodland cover in the year 2000. We calculated speed as the maximum rate of change of woodland loss through the time-period, and as fragmentation as the maximum value of edge density of the spatial pattern of woodland loss through the time-period. We categorized the activeness of the frontier based on when in the time-period the frontier was detected. Finally, we considered the extent of woodlands left after the period of woodland loss analysed (see Supplementary Text 1 and Supplementary Figure 2).

In step 3, we combined the frontier metrics into three thematic typologies. To do so, we first classified each metric into three classes, informed by data or literature when available (see Supplementary Text 1). Our first thematic typology focuses on severity, and we combined baseline woodland with total percentage of total woodland loss to show the accumulated impact of the frontier over the period analysed. The rationale for this typology is that the accumulated impact of deforestation frontiers can result from frontier actors' varied ability to capture rents^{13,36}. A second thematic typology focused on spatial and temporal patterns, where we paired speed and fragmentation to show how frontiers progress. The rationale is that the spatio-temporal patterns in frontiers result from different contexts underlying frontier expansion. For instance, commodity-driven frontiers might result in faster and less fragmented frontier progression, given their higher access to technologies and capital^{36,65,66}. Our third thematic typology represents the frontier development stage, where we paired activeness of the frontier with the amount of forest left to understand when a frontier was active, and the potential of further frontier activity. This typology further allows us to indicate the status of the frontier in a pre-to-post frontier gradient^{13,36,67}. To identify frontier types for each of our three thematic typologies, we classified each frontier metric into three sub-classes. This classification follows former frontier studies^{13,36} and a set of heuristic rules that best represented variability in our metrics. This yielded nine frontier types per thematic typology (more information on each metric in Supplementary Text 1).

In step 4, we qualitatively grouped frontier types in a second level of high-level frontier archetypes by combining specific types, based on the most prevalent types and insightful combinations thereof, potentially reflecting distinct mechanisms of frontier development, and configurations of commodity frontiers, post frontiers, smallholder frontiers, and pioneer frontiers^{13,36,43}. These archetypes were built to provide a coherent understanding of the most common frontier patterns, complementing the full description of frontiers captured by the

typologies. Thus, not all frontiers are included in our archetypes, and future studies could adjust our archetypes to highlight different, or more, archetypes based on the specific goals of the analyses. In other words, our archetype exercise is an approach that can be purposefully adapted, and our implementation serves as an example. Finally, we quantified the extent of frontier types and archetypes, as well as the total area occupied by frontiers. We further quantified the proportions of frontier types and archetypes within continents and ecoregions. For visualization purposes, in frontier types and archetypes maps (Figure 2 to 5), we applied a moving window calculation based on the modal value of neighbourhood 3x3 grid cells. The combination of our thematic typologies (step 3) and our archetypes (step 4) allows us to structure complexity in frontier processes and explore emerging patterns at high thematic resolution, while identifying high-level, recurring frontier archetypes with high generalization potential.

Characteristics of deforestation frontiers. To further characterize our frontiers, we identified a set of spatial determinants (see Supplementary Text 2) building on theories of frontiers, land rent theory and location theory^{8,36,43}. We used four global datasets. First, we used a classification of the dominant drivers of tree loss (e.g., commodity-driven forest loss)⁶⁸. Second, we used a dataset on field size, as large fields sizes proxy capital inputs to farming⁶⁹. Third, to characterize market accessibility, we used a dataset of travel time to cities⁷⁰. Finally, we used a dataset that proxies agricultural suitability⁷¹, via the summed agroclimatic potential for low-input, rainfed agriculture of main crops and commodities. For the forest loss driver's dataset, particularly in Africa, the class "shifting agriculture" encompasses various forms of subsistence and market-oriented forms of agriculture practiced by smallholders. In Africa specifically, the importance of shifting agriculture in a strict sense has been decreasing recently⁷². We thus refer to the shifting agriculture class as "smallholder agriculture" in our manuscript, encompassing shifting agriculture as well as other forms of smallholder agriculture. Each characterizing variable had five categories (see Supplementary Text 2). We overlaid the deforestation frontier types with all spatial determinants. We extracted the median value of each spatial determinant per pixel of analyzed frontiers and then calculated the share of each spatial determinant category for each type and archetype. The dominant drivers of forest loss dataset did not overlap with 5.4% of our frontiers, and field size dataset with 54.70% of our frontiers. For each combination, frontiers with no overlapped were not displayed in the results.

Research effort across frontier types. To evaluate past research effort on deforestation in tropical dry woodlands, and how research effort relates to our frontier types, we carried out a

systematic literature review following the PRISMA approach⁷³. We selected a set of keywords characterizing the object of study (tropical dry woodlands) and process studied (woodland loss). We tested keywords interactively in the ISI Web of Knowledge. We finally used the following search string: *("Frontier*" OR "Defor*") AND ("*Dry Forest*" OR "*Savanna*" OR "Dry tropical forest*" OR "woodland*")*. We searched using these keywords in July 2019 in the ISI Web of Knowledge and Scopus databases, yielding 2,146 records. We removed duplicates, leaving 1,439 records (see Supplementary Figure 7).

We then reviewed the remaining records using an inclusion criterion by reading, depending on necessity, the title, abstract and then the full text. The inclusion criteria retained papers that quantitatively or qualitatively analyzed forest loss in our study area. We included papers that directly or indirectly calculated or inferred forest loss to analyze other social-ecological components (e.g., carbon storage) if the forest loss data were disclosed. We finally selected 155 records for further analysis. Next, we reviewed the full text of each of these records to classify each record on geographical location, ecoregion studied, and spatial and temporal scale of the analysis. We georeferenced these records to ecoregions resolution.

To relate frontier archetypes with research effort, we compared the occurrence of each ecoregion's frontier archetypes with the number of studies per ecoregion. For that we calculated a weighted occurrence of archetypes by number of studies, by multiplying the share of archetypes by the share of records found in each ecoregion. We then summed the ecoregion level weighted occurrences by archetype and divided it by total share of archetype and by continent, resulting in the research effort bias by archetype and by continent, respectively.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All datasets used here are publicly available and referenced. Data outputs from this study are publicly available on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6141799>. Methodological steps are described in Methods section and in Supplementary Information.

CODE AVAILABILITY

The code used for the development of frontier metrics, typologies and archetypes in this study is permanently and publicly available on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6141799>.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

A.B., T.K. M.B., and P.M. designed the research idea. A.B. and M.B., collected the data. A.B. led the designed the analytical framework and led the data analysis. A.B. led the writing, M.B., P.M. and T.K. contributed to the interpretation of results and the writing of the manuscript.

COMPETING INTERESTS STATEMENT

The authors declare no competing interests.

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